

Substantiation of effective land reclamation methods based on the assessment of the physicochemical properties of saline soils in the Syrdarya region of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. The article presents new effective technologies for desalinating saline soils with complex water-physical and chemical properties. Technologies for reducing soil salinity, alternative to winter washing with a layer of water, are proposed. In the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region, the effectiveness of furrow irrigation using the Biosolvent soil conditioner (pH~2) was studied. Water-saving methods for increasing the leaching of soil salts using deep soil loosening and treatment with a preparation containing organic acids have been experimentally proven: a) decreasing of salinization of abandoned lands with atmospheric precipitation; b) leaching of salinized soils with water supply to furrows. Scientific publications and our own materials have been analysed, and the reasons for the low water permeability and bad leaching of salt of the studied serozem-meadow soils have been identified: increased content of calcium carbonates in the soil and magnesium, - in the soil absorption complex. A direct relationship was established between the reduction in absorbed magnesium content and of toxic salts in the soil. Experiments have proven that the filtration properties of soil can be improved by: a) deep loosening of compacted carbonate soils; b) treating the soil with organic acid, which reduces the magnesium content of the absorption complex.

1 Introduction

The Syrdarya Region of Uzbekistan is located in the middle reaches of the Syr Darya River and is part of the newly reclaimed territory of the Hungry Steppe. A distinctive feature of the newly reclaimed lands is the presence of soils with unfavorable hydrophysical and chemical properties. According to the Institute of Soil Science and Agrochemistry of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 177,046 hectares of irrigated land in the region, or 61.7%, are

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represented by low-permeability soils. In the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya Region, out of 29,900 hectares of irrigated land, 21,000 hectares, or 51.2%, have low soil permeability. Of the 287,100 hectares of irrigated land in the Syrdarya Region, 97% of the soil is consistently saline, of which 24.7% has a moderate to high degree of salinity. In the Mirzaabad district, 91% of the 29.9 thousand hectares of irrigated land are salinized, 29% of which have a moderate to high degree of salinization.

Due to climate change in Uzbekistan, water availability is projected to decrease by 25% by 2050. Currently, the Republic is implementing large-scale water conservation measures in irrigation: water-saving irrigation technologies (drip irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, laser field leveling, discrete irrigation, etc.) are being introduced, and canal lining is being carried out on a large scale. To maintain a favorable soil salinity regime, saline soils are leached during the non-growing season, requiring large volumes of water (up to 4,000 m³/ha). Under current conditions, there is a need to reduce the amount of water used for leaching saline soils.

Therefore, the effectiveness of soil desalination using the well-known technology of leaching with a layer of water in checks is problematic. Furthermore, it has been experimentally proven that this leaching technology is water-intensive and leads to soil compaction.

The authors of this article conducted research on three new water-saving technologies for desalination of soils in the Mirzaabad district with low water permeability and weak leaching of salts. As alternatives to leaching with a sheet of water, the following are proposed: a) a leaching irrigation regime, b) the use of atmospheric precipitation, and c) furrow leaching using the Biosolvent ameliorant (pH 2), created with an organic acid. This article also aims to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the causes of low filtration and salt release in soils in this region based on a study of their physicochemical properties and to propose appropriate (adequate) innovative reclamation methods. The causes of unfavorable hydrophysical soil properties and possible methods for their improvement are examined in detail.

The recommendations were developed on the basis of comprehensive experimental studies, a detailed assessment of the physicochemical properties of sierozem-meadow soils, and the identification of the causes of low water permeability and salt release of soils and empirical dependencies on chemical processes in the soil.

2 Materials and methods

Three water-saving soil desalination technologies were tested in the Mirzaabad district. 1. Creating a leaching irrigation regime for cotton [1]. Method essence: before the first irrigation of cotton on saline soils, to enhance salt leaching, the soil was treated with Biosolvent (pH = 1.9). 2. A technology for desalinizing the soil of highly saline abandoned lands using atmospheric precipitation, during autumn field preparation using deep loosening, with soil treatment with Biosolvent before precipitation. 3. Leaching saline soils in early spring by furrows, with small volumes of water, also using loosening and a biopreparation. Since the soils had unfavorable properties, they were studied in detail during the experiments.

Methods for determining the hydrophysical properties of soils in the experimental plot: bulk density (soil bulk density) - by the cutting ring method, water permeability - by the double ring method. Laboratory soil analyses were performed using generally accepted methods in accordance with GOSTs and the methodology for performing chemical soil analyses (according to E.V. Arinushkina). The mechanical composition (particle size distribution) of the soil was determined by the Stokes method, gypsum, carbonates - by the hydrochloric acid extract method, the chemical composition of the soil - by the water

extract method; the composition of cations in the SAC according to Gedroits. Electrical conductivity (ECe) and pH were measured using calibrated devices: a conductometer and a pH meter. Graphical and statistical processing of laboratory and field study data to identify interrelations and patterns of soil properties and test hypotheses was performed in Excel. The data from field and laboratory studies on soil properties were processed statistically, equations for the relationships between the indicators were determined.

To interpret the results of field studies and laboratory analysis data, and to identify relationships and patterns, laboratory archive materials and published sources containing theoretical and experimental scientific data were used.

2.1 Soil characteristics

The main soil properties of the experimental plot, determined in field and laboratory studies, are presented in Tables 1-4.

The soils are medium to light loamy in terms of particle size distribution. At a depth of 80-100 cm and below, there is a gypsum layer of up to 8.7%, and the carbonate content is uniform throughout the profile, ranging from 16.8 to 20.2%. A distinctive feature of the soil is the abnormally high content of absorbed magnesium throughout the profile. Absorbed magnesium accounts for 50-73% of the total bases (4.0-5.5 mg-eq per 100 g of soil), while the absorbed calcium content is 18-54% of the total bases (1.4-3.6 mg-eq per 100 g). In this case, the sum of absorbed bases is 6.85 - 8.50 mg-eq. per 100 g of soil. The studied soils have very low water permeability: 0.01-0.017 m/day. Soil salinity is uneven across the profile. According to the main assessment indicators (Table 3), salinization varies from moderate to high (according to ECe) in the range from 6.04 to 13.76 dS/m; according to solid residue – from 0.51 to 1.47%; according to chloride ion – from 0.04 to 0.14% of the soil mass. The relationship between the content of solid residue in % and ECe dS/m is as follows:

$$Y (\text{Dense residue}) = 0.124 * X(\text{ECe}) - 0.206; R^2 = 0.957 \tag{1}$$

The type of soil salinization is chloride-sulfate and sulfate-chloride. The maximum salt content was noted in the 80-100 cm layer, where the gypsum accumulation was also found. Toxic salts in this layer contain 0.455-0.717% of the soil mass, and in other cases, 0.204-0.437%. With an absorption capacity of 6.85 to 8.50 mg-eq/100 g of soil, the Ca content in the SAC is 18-54%, with a Mg content of 50-73%, i.e., Mg in the SAC exceeds Ca by 1.1-4.0 times. The high content of exchangeable magnesium, significantly exceeding the content of absorbed calcium, is illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The ratio of magnesium and calcium in the soil absorption complex (the amount of absorbed sodium is 0.09 - 0.87 mg-eq. / 100 g of soil).

Table 1. Chemical composition of the soil in the experimental plot in the Mirzaabad district.

Horizon, cm	ECe, dS/m	TDS, %	Content of soluble ions, %						
			HCO ₃ '	Cl'	SO ["] ₄	Ca	Mg	Na'	K'
Soil profile 1									
0-22	6.0	0.514	0.024	0.039	0.272	0.076	0.016	0.043	0.004
22-51	7.1	0.648	0.020	0.063	0.336	0.072	0.026	0.075	0.003
51-71	7.2	0.62	0.024	0.081	0.3	0.072	0.022	0.078	0.002
71-100*	12.3	1.336	0.017	0.081	0.768	0.222	0.041	0.09	0.002
100-125	9.0	1.06	0.015	0.039	0.576	0.176	0.025	0.052	0.002
> 125	10.8	1.064	0.015	0.119	0.576	0.154	0.038	0.11	0.002
Soil profile 2									
0-40	9.0	0.928	0.021	0.053	0.52	0.132	0.03	0.075	0.006
40-80	10.3	1.046	0.016	0.056	0.6	0.146	0.029	0.1	0.003
80-120*	13.8	1.466	0.017	0.14	0.8	0.192	0.048	0.17	0.002
140-170	8.3	0.816	0.015	0.042	0.49	0.132	0.029	0.06	0.002

Table 2. Chemical composition of the soil in the experimental plot in the Mirzaabad district.

Horizon, cm	Absorbed cations, mg-eq/100 g					Gypsum CaSO ₄ *2H ₂ O, %	Calcium carbonate CaCO ₃ , %	pH	Na', mg-eq./100 g
	Ca	Mg	Na'	K'	Total				
Soil profile 1									
0-22	3.6	3.9	0.3	0.1	8.0	0.59	20.2	8.5	1.87
22-51	2.8	4.3	0.3	0.2	7.6	0.72	19.7	8.5	3.26
51-71	2.4	5.1	0.2	0.4	8.1	1.35	19.3	8.5	3.39
71-100*	1.8	4.7	0.2	0.1	6.9	8.68	18.0	8.3	3.92
100-125	2.4	1.8	0.2	0.1	4.4	4.02	17.6	8.3	2.26
> 125	2.0	4.7	0.2	0.1	7.0	6.47	16.8	8.3	4.79
Soil profile 2									
0-40	2.2	5.1	0.4	0.8	8.5	0.98	19.0	8.5	3.26
40-80	2.0	4.7	0.3	0.6	7.6	4.01	19.2	8.6	4.35
80-120*	1.4	5.5	0.2	0.4	7.6	8.77	19.5	8.4	7.40
140-170	1.8	3.9	0.3	0.9	6.9	3.14	19.7	8.5	2.61

*Horizons with the maximum content of gypsum and water-soluble salts.

Table 3. Characteristics of the physical and chemical properties of soils of the experimental site in the Mirzaabad district and their comparison with the soils of the Sardoba district of the Syrdarya region.

Indicators	Units of measures	Mirzaabad district		Sardoba district**	
Established filtration	m/day	0.01-0.017		0.03...0.07	
ECe	dS/m	6.04 -13.76*		He onp.	
Average density in a meter-thick layer	g/cm ³	0-40 cm 1.56-1.78	> 40 cm 1.42-1.53	1.39	
Content of fraction, 0.05-0.01 mm	% by mass	41.50-45.83		28.52	
Gypsum content	% by mass	0.59-8.77*		6.51...16.05	
Carbonate content, CaCO ₃	% by mass	16.8-20.2		5.27-9.81	
Content of TDS/chlorine ion in soil	% by mass	0.083 -1.147*		2.238 a)	1.208 b)
The amount of toxic salts	% by mass	0.204 - 0.437*		1.278 a)	0.233 b)
Content of chlorine ion in soil	% by mass	0.039-0.140*		0.327 a)	0.015 b)
Magnesium content in soil (based on water extract),	% by mass	0.026-0.036*		0.045 a)	0.016 b)
Magnesium content in the SAC	mg-eq. per 100 g of soil)% of the SAC	(4.0-5.5)/50-73		4.30/50 a)	1.00/18 b)
Calcium content in the SAC		(1.4-3.6)/18-54		0.80/8.5 a)	4.86/76 b)

*Maximum content in the layer 70-120 cm (gypsum-containing horizon).

**Experiments on 1m soil monoliths: a)- before leaching; b)- after leaching at a rate of 20 thousand m³/ha.

Table 4. Classification of soil salinity assessment.

Degree of soil salinization	ECe, dS/m [2]	by Cl ⁻ , % [3]	by Na ⁺ , mg-eq/100 g of soil
Not salted	0-2	< 0.02	< 1
Slightly saline	2-4.	0.02-0.035	1.0-3.0
Moderately saline	4-8.	0.035-0.07	3.1-6.0
Highly saline	8-16.	0.07-0.14	6.1-12.0
Very heavily salted	>16	> 0.14	12.1-28.0

3 Research Results

The effectiveness of soil desalination in three studied water-saving technologies:

1. Soil desalination during cotton furrow irrigation by increasing salt leaching (creating an enhanced leaching irrigation regime) through furrow treatment with Biosolvent, an organic acid-based product (pH 2). The water consumption for the leaching portion together with irrigation was 1000 m³ ha, the consumption of the preparation was 5 l/ha, the increase in salt leaching in the studied variant, compared to the control (normal irrigation) was: 48% for the total amount of salts and 29% for the chloride ion (Figure 2) [1].

Fig. 2. Reduction in the content of salts and ions in the 0-70 cm layer, under the influence of the use of Biosolvent, during the first vegetation irrigation of cotton by furrows (the experiment is described in the article [1], moderately saline soils EC_e = 6-7 dS/m).

Fig. 3. Effect of the combined effect of loosening and Biosolvent on the leaching of ions and salts during soil leaching along furrows (average of three replicates, product consumption 5 l/ha, initial EC_e 9.0 dS/m, highly saline soils).

2. The efficiency of soil desalination technology under the influence of atmospheric precipitation with preliminary deep loosening of the soil 0-70 cm and subsequent treatment with Biosolvent (10 l/ha) before precipitation (according to the forecast) is shown in Table 5.

Table 4 shows that deep loosening alone is significantly more effective at leaching salts from compacted soils. The impact of Biosolvent is noticeable against the backdrop of repeated high-quality soil loosening in 2022. According to the table, while the leaching of total salts from 2022 to 2023 under the control (loosening without Biosolvent) was 24% for the EU and 28% for the compacted residue, with the use of Biosolvent, these figures increased to 41% and 40%, respectively. For magnesium and toxic salts, the increase in leaching with the use of Biosolvent was 25% and 35%, respectively.

Table 5. Changes in soil salinity indicators during soil desalination by atmospheric precipitation

Indicators	Options	Initial Dec 2021.	Dec 2022	Apr 2023	Change Dec 2022- Apr 2023, %	Changes Dec 2021 – Apr 2023	
						ECe, dS/m	% of initial
ECe, dS/m	Experience (e)	12.2	9	5.1	-41	-7.1	-58
	Control (c)	15.2	8.9	6.8	-24	-8.4	-55
	Difference (e-c)	-3	0.08	-1.7	17	-1.3	
	Difference (e-c),%			-25			
Total dissolved salts,%	Experience (e)	1.36	1.04	0.58	-40	-0.78	-57
	Control (c)	1.68	1.07	0.75	-28	-0.93	-55
	Difference (e-c)	-0.32	-0.02	-0.17	12	-0.15	
	Difference (e-c),%			-23			
Cl ⁻ , %	Experience (e)	0.11	0.07	0.02	-71	-0.09	-82
	Control (c)	0.16	0.05	0.02	-60	-0.14	-88
	Difference (e-c)	-0.04	0.02	0	11	-0.04	
	Difference (e-c),%			0			
SO ⁴ 4%	Experience (e)	0.75	0.59	0.31	-47	-0.44	-59
	Control (c)	0.93	0.64	0.42	-35	-0.51	-55
	Difference (e-c)	-0.18	-0.05	-0.11	12	-0.07	
	Difference (e-c),%			-26			
Ca, %	Experience (e)	0.13	0.12	0.07	-31	-0.06	-46
	Control (c)	0.14	0.17	0.1	-7	-0.04	-29
	Difference (e-c)	-0.01	-0.05	-0.03	24	0.02	
	Difference (e-c),%			-30			
Mg, %	Experience (e)	0.07	0.04	0.03	-25	-0.04	-57
	Control (c)	0.06	0.03	0.03	0	-0.03	-50
	Difference (e-c)	0.01	0.01	0	25	-0.01	
	Difference (e-c),%			0			
Sum of toxic salts	Experience (e)	0.79	0.74	0.28	-62	-0.51	-65
	Control (c)	1.05	0.56	0.41	-27	-0.64	-61
	Difference (e-c)	-0.26	0.18	-0.13	35	0.13	
	Difference (e-c),%			-32			

* The amount of atmospheric precipitation in 2021-2022 is 302 mm, in 2022-2023 it is 174 mm, the consumption rate of the preparation is 10 l/ha.

3. The effectiveness of furrow leaching with preliminary loosening to a depth of 70 cm in the fall and treatment of the field surface (furrows) with the product before watering, at a water supply rate of 1,400 m³/ha and a product consumption rate of 5 l/ha, demonstrated high efficiency in leaching ions and salts (Figure 3, Table 6).

According to the data provided (Table 5), for individual replicates of the experiment, leaching of toxic salts reached 47.5-59.5% of the original content, with an average

reduction of 51.3%. This demonstrates that furrow leaching with low water consumption (1,400 m³/ha) is quite effective.

Table 6. Change in the content of hypothetical salts during soil leaching along furrows (with soil loosening and treatment with Biosolvent, water supply 1400 m³/ha)

Indicators		Repetitions			Average	Average deviation
		LB2*	LB5	LB28		
Ca(HCO ₃) ₂	Before leaching	0.010	0.012	0.008	0.010	0.00
	After leaching	0.012	0.011	0.015	0.013	0.00
	Difference	0.002	-0.001	0.006	0.003	0.00
	%	25.0	-6.7	80.0	32.8	31.5
CaSO ₄	Before leaching	0.325	0.500	0.422	0.416	0.06
	After leaching	0.330	0.474	0.314	0.373	0.07
	Difference	0.005	-0.027	-0.108	-0.043	0.04
	%	1.5	-5.3	-25.5	-9.8	10.5
MgSO ₄	Before leaching	0.238	0.238	0.226	0.234	0.01
	After leaching	0.137	0.214	0.113	0.154	0.04
	Difference	-0.101	-0.024	-0.113	-0.079	0.04
	%	-42.5	-10.0	-50.0	-34.2	16.1
Na ₂ SO ₄	Before leaching	0.350	0.426	0.267	0.348	0.05
	After leaching	0.116	0.141	0.133	0.130	0.01
	Difference	-0.234	-0.285	-0.134	-0.218	0.06
	%	-66.8	-67.0	-50.3	-61.4	7.4
NaCl	Before leaching	0.179	0.139	0.040	0.119	0.05
	After leaching	0.058	0.081	0.029	0.056	0.02
	Difference	-0.121	-0.058	-0.012	-0.063	0.04
	%	-67.7	-41.7	-28.6	-46.0	14.5
Sum of toxic salts	Before leaching	0.767	0.802	0.533	0.701	0.11
	After leaching	0.311	0.435	0.274	0.340	0.06
	Difference	-0.456	-0.367	-0.259	-0.361	0.07
	%	-59.5	-45.7	-48.5	-51.3	5.5

* LB2 - Loosening + Biosolvent (2-point), LB5 - Loosening + Biosolvent (5-point), LB8 - Loosening + Biosolvent (5-point).

From the data shown in Table 6 and Figure 3, it is evident that the above-described improved low-water-consuming soil desalination technology, combining loosening with Biosolvent, with two different water supply technologies (precipitation 174 mm and furrow

leaching 1400 m³/ha), allows to reduce soil salinization by toxic salts by 51-62%, and the amount of water-soluble magnesium by 25-34% of the original content.

4 Discussion

While studying the water-saving technologies described above, unfavorable soil properties were identified; literary sources were consulted to determine the causes [4-8].

From an analysis of the published works reviewed regarding the unfavorable filtration and other soil properties of the Hungry Steppe, their causes, and the patterns identified by the authors and researchers [5-8], [9-10], [14], the causes of soil density and low water permeability are clearly:

- the presence of carbonates (approximately 20%), which accounts for the very high density of the topsoil (up to 1.78 g/cm³);
- a combination of gypsum and carbonates in the 80-100 cm horizon (the abrupt increase in salt content in this layer indicates that this horizon is the one that blocks water from penetrating downwards);
- a high content of absorbed magnesium (3.95 - 5.52 mg-eq/100 g), which exceeds the calcium content in the SAC by 1.1 to 4.0 times.

According to research conducted by the V.V. Dokuchaev Soil Science Institute, the territory of the Hungry Steppe (Zaamin alluvial fan) is characterized by complex meliorative conditions determined by their lithological-granulometric composition, gypsum content, carbonation, and salinity of the soil profile. According to E.I. Pankova and co-authors, "the properties of most soils in the Zaamin alluvial fan, from the point of view of water-physical indicators, should be assessed as extremely unfavorable [4]. Thus, due to high salinity, gypsum content and lithological features, the soils in the Zaamin alluvial fan should be classified as difficult to reclaim soils" [4]. This definition corresponds to the soil-reclamation conditions of the object of our research in the Mirzaabad district, which is confirmed by the soil properties of the experimental site, which are reflected in Table 1.

The effects of elevated calcium carbonate content in soils are described in publications [8]. Citing the FAO publication [11], the authors note that "as CaCO₃ content increases to 20 or 25%, carbonate precipitation in capillary tubes leads to an increase in the proportion of very fine pores and a decrease in moisture movement." Source [11] indicates that "surface crust formation can be a serious problem on newly irrigated calcareous soils, especially those with low organic matter content. Bulk density values of 1.7 g/cm³ or higher (except in very sandy soils) may indicate the presence of a surface crust." The above confirms the problems of the influence of carbonates on soil infiltration in the experimental field in Mirzaabad.

Thus, one of the main reasons for the high density of the upper soil horizons and low permeability before leaching at our site is presumably the presence of carbonates, which make up approximately 20% of the soil surface (Table 3).

From the above data on the unfavorable soil properties of the study site and the interpretation of the causes, it appears that these lands are very difficult to restore and improve their productivity using traditional methods of leaching with a layer of water by checks.

An analysis of the sources revealed that one of the main causes of the high density of the upper soil horizons and low water permeability in the experimental plot is presumably the presence of carbonates, which constitute approximately 20% of the soil surface. This deficiency can be corrected by deep soil loosening. Based on the location of the gypsum horizon below 70 cm, loosening should be carried out to a depth of up to 1 meter.

Another reason for low water infiltration into the soil is the high magnesium content in the adsorption complex (SAC), which significantly exceeds the content of adsorbed

calcium. Under these conditions, according to the authors [5-7], magnesium negatively impacts the filtration properties of the soil.

To identify the causes and patterns of the development of the aforementioned unfavorable soil properties in the study area, in addition to processing our own data, we considered theoretical hypotheses, examined published review articles on the topic, and analyzed the results of scientific and analytical experimental studies.

From an analysis of a number of published sources, the authors' previous research experience on leaching saline soils in the Syrdarya region, and a review of soil data from the experimental site, it follows that low soil permeability is a very important indicator for soil leaching, reflecting a combination of negative soil properties: carbonate content, density, gypsum content, salt chemical composition, and the ratio of cations in the Soil Absorption Complex.

The parameters listed in Table 1-bulk density, infiltration, carbonate content, and the aforementioned magnesium content in the exchangeable soil complex-are not optimal for ensuring soil fertility.

A significant excess of absorbed magnesium over calcium in the soils of the Golodnaya and Jizzakh steppes is noted [12], which is termed magnesium solonetzic soils. Other literature sources [13] indicate that "In soils with a high carbonate content, high exchangeable magnesium in the exchangeable soil complex is sometimes observed, which can affect soil structure, increase alkalinity, and alter water conductivity. Increased magnesium in the exchangeable soil complex can degrade soil structure, reduce water permeability, and lead to compaction, which negatively impacts fertility."

In a detailed analytical review, the authors [5] note that "Magnesium can affect the physical properties of soils, which are especially important under irrigated conditions: particle size distribution and aggregate composition; structural state; specific and bulk density; porosity; air, water, thermal, electrical and radioactive properties, hardness; plasticity; viscosity; stickiness; fluidity; shrinkage; resistance to tearing, compression, torsion; soil friction on soil; soil friction on metal; specific soil resistance during cultivation; soil resistance to the movement of machines and tools." The authors also note that "Literary sources constantly mention the deterioration of the physical properties of soils under the influence of high magnesium content. In this case, the soils exhibit properties characteristic of soils with a high sodium content (monosodium solonetz), while the sodium content in the studied soils is noted at a low level, that is, the soils have physical solonetzism. Since the second half of the 20th century, some researchers have referred to soils with an absorbed magnesium content of 25% or more of their exchange capacity as magnesian or magnesium solonetz. In their conclusion, the authors write, "The adverse effects of magnesium are generally not characteristic of soils with an exchangeable Ca:Mg ratio greater than 1; when Mg predominates over Ca, clay dispersion occurs, the content of blocky aggregates increases, and the effect of exchangeable sodium intensifies, which begins to manifest itself when the Mg content exceeds 30% of the total base cations. Soils with a high smectite (montmorillonite) content are particularly sensitive to changes in magnesium content."

«High magnesium waters and soils are emerging examples of water quality deterioration and land degradation leading to environmental and food security constraints in several irrigation schemes. A ratio of magnesium-to-calcium > 1 in irrigation waters and an exchangeable magnesium percentage $> 25\%$ in soils are considered high enough to result in soil degradation and impact crop yields negatively» [6].

Long-term studies [7] have established that "in soils irrigated with mineralized water, the amount of absorbed magnesium is significantly higher than the amount of sodium. With increasing duration of use of these waters, the amount of exchangeable magnesium increases." No progressive accumulation of absorbed sodium was recorded. When

magnesium replaces some of the absorbed calcium, the physical properties of the soil deteriorate. This results in a significant increase in bulk density to 1.5–1.6 g/cm³, a decrease in porosity to 35–40%, and a sharp decline in filtration capacity. The filtration coefficient of these soils decreases by a factor of 3–4 compared to soil irrigated with irrigation water. In soils with more than 50% of the absorbed magnesium absorption capacity, the dispersion coefficient is 10–20%, while in soils containing 30–50% of the absorbed sodium, it reaches 50–60%. Thus, the consequences of replacing some of the absorbed bases with sodium cause severe soil dispersion and, consequently, a decrease in its filtration capacity. Saturation of the absorbing complex with magnesium does not disperse the soil, and the deterioration in its filtration is associated with compaction and cementation of the soil profile. The authors called this process "magnesium slitization." It is very clearly expressed in soils irrigated with mineralized water for long periods of time."

Source [14] also notes that in alkaline soils, with an increase in the amount of magnesium in the SEC and a change in the Ca:Mg ratio towards magnesium, environmentally unfavorable changes, a "disharmony" of the soil environment, may occur. Increasing magnesium in the soil-exchange complex maintains the alkalinity of soils and, in some cases, even leads to the formation of special soils-magnesium solonchaks. In the presence of magnesium carbonates and bicarbonates in the soil, magnesium causes an increase in alkalinity. With a high content of exchangeable magnesium, the solubility of humic substances increases and the soil structure deteriorates, water permeability decreases, which negatively affects the water regime. High levels of exchangeable magnesium intensify the negative effects of exchangeable sodium, even though its content in the soil is low.

According to the characteristics of highly saline soils in the Sardoba district of the Syrdarya region, given in Table 3, they also had an increased magnesium content in the SAC (50%), with a ratio of Mg : Ca = 4.30 : 0.80. By leaching 1-meter-deep soil monoliths at very high rates (20,000 m³/ha), a decrease in the magnesium content in the Soil Absorbed Complex and a Mg:Ca ratio of 1.08:4.86 was achieved (see Table 3). This example demonstrates that leaching at low water rates is unlikely to resolve the problem of displacing exchangeable magnesium from the soil (given its high content in the SAC) to improve the hydro physical properties of the soil, including increasing water infiltration into the soil.

An analysis of the relationship equations obtained on the basis of processing data from two soil profiles in the experimental area (Table 7) shows the influence of calcium and magnesium in the aqueous extract on the content of absorbed magnesium in the studied saline soils (ECe in the 0-70 cm layer = 6.8 - 9.7 dS/m, ECe max in the 70-120 cm layer - 13.8 dS/m).

An inverse relationship was established between the content of absorbed calcium and the content of absorbed magnesium ($y = -0.68x + 5.39$), as well as with water-soluble calcium ($y = -0.19x + 3.49$) (Table 6).

The content of absorbed magnesium is also negatively related to the presence of water-soluble calcium in the soil ($y = -0.67x + 3.92$).

The data suggest that absorbed magnesium is not displaced by calcium as the calcium content in the aqueous extract increases. This issue needs to be studied in the context of soil dynamics (changes in salinity and soil absorbed complexes during irrigation and leaching).

Table 7. Equations for the relationship of Ca and Mg ions in the SAC and in the aqueous extract based on data from sections at the experimental site in the Mirzaabad district

Y	X	Equation	Correlation coefficient
Mg absorption	Ca aqueous extract	$y = -0.67x + 3.92$	$R^2 = 0.711$
Mg absorption.	Mg aqueous extract	$y = 0.38x + 3.72$	$R^2 = 0.338$
Ca absorption	Ca aqueous extract	$y = -0.19x + 3.49$	$R^2 = 0.615$
Ca absorption	Mg absorption	$y = -0.68x + 5.39$	$R^2 = 0.313$

Figure 4 shows two empirical relationships showing a linear positive relationship between soil salinity in terms of the sum of toxic salts and the magnesium content in the Soil Absorbed Complex.

Fig. 4. Equations for the relationship between magnesium content in the SAC and the content of toxic salts in the soil for the conditions of the Syrdarya region.

The established pattern indicates the possibility of a decrease in magnesium in the soil absorption complex during soil desalination.

Using the equation in Figure 4 for soils in the Mirzaabad district:

$$y = -2,702x + 3,592 \quad R^2 = 0,53 \quad (2)$$

$$Y_{(\text{absorbed magnesium})} = -2,702 * X_{(\Sigma \text{toxical salts})} + 3,592 \quad (3)$$

and substituting the values for the total toxic salts from Table 6 (before and after leaching), we obtain a positive prediction: furrow leaching with the use of loosening and Biosolvent will reduce the absorbed magnesium by 1 mg-eq/100 g of soil (from 5.5 to 4.5).

Thus, the established pattern—a positive correlation between the content of absorbed and water-soluble magnesium, as well as confirmed experimental data on the effectiveness of salt leaching with Biosolvent—indicates the possibility of reducing the magnesium content in the soil absorption complex and, accordingly, improving soil properties.

5 Conclusion

1. The authors' research substantiates the possibility of enhancing the leaching of salts and reducing water consumption using soil desalination technologies that are alternative to leaching with a layer of water: a) leaching irrigation regime, b) use of atmospheric precipitation, c) two-stroke leaching along furrows using the Biosolvent ameliorant (pH ~ 2), created on the basis of an organic acid. Soil loosening promotes the leaching of the total amount of salts from the 0-30 cm layer by atmospheric precipitation, from 25 to 55%, depending on the initial soil salinity and precipitation. The quality of soil loosening plays an important role;

2. It has been established that to improve the filtration properties of the soil, it is necessary to reduce the content of absorbed magnesium and increase the content of absorbed calcium, which can be achieved by leaching the soil with high volumes of water under provided drainage, which is not possible under conditions of water scarcity; In the conditions of the inevitability of the transition to the economical use of limited water resources, both for irrigation and for the reclamation of saline lands, the study of international approaches to the management of the salt regime of irrigated soils, in combination with the analysis of experimental data conducted in specific local conditions, using different soil desalination technologies, allows us to take a broader look at the problem;

3. Experimental data have shown that the application of the organic acid-based ameliorant Biosolvent increases the leaching of toxic salts by 51-62%, while the amount of water-soluble magnesium decreases by 25-34% compared to the soil loosening method. The cited research data on water-saving soil desalination technologies (1-3) demonstrate their effectiveness and the possibility of maintaining a favorable salt regime in complex carbonate soils with elevated exchangeable magnesium content;

4. Presumably, an increase/decrease in soil salinity may also lead to an increase/decrease in the content of absorbed magnesium in the SAC. The direction of these processes can worsen (or improve) the hydrophysical properties of soils, so it is necessary to regularly monitor soil salinity and maintain a negative salt balance in the soil, including using the proposed.

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